

An experience of crowdfunding supporting herbarium collection in Ukraine

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Annotation: Краудфандинг – перспективна технологія залучення коштів невеликими порціями від значного числа беккерів, яка, однак, доволі рідко використовується науці і, тим паче, українській. Ми спробували шляхом винагородного краудфандингу вирішити поточну кризову ситуацію в гербарії LWS, яка склалася за відсутності фінансування. В результаті було отримано 33322,31 грн. (~ \$1,333) надходжень, що відповідає 87,3% від первинної цілі проекту і загалом свідчить про його успішність.

Keywords: scientific fundraising, reward-based crowdfunding, biological collections conservation

Ключові слова: науковий фандрайзинг, винагородний краудфандинг, збереження біологічних колекцій

Crowdfunding is not a new technology, arisen from bootstrapping support and successfully applied for decades by profit and nonprofit organizations (Tomczak and Brem 2013). Idea of gathering funds by small portions from different outsources became a vital technology first among artists and small creative projects, later spread to other market sectors including science (Kraus et al. 2016, Vachelard et al. 2016) and biology in particular (Li and Pryer 2014, Gallo-Cajiao et al. 2018). Dorfman (2017) designated crowdfunding among substantial technologies in management of modern museums of natural history.

In 2018 we have been faced with unconventional situation at the Herbarium of the State Museum of Natural History of the NAS of Ukraine (LWS) – we found that many of folders are damaged, while general conditions are far from optimal for preservation of herbarium material. AN, as a scientific curator of LWS, reported about this critical situation and asked the directorate of museum for support. However, due to lack of financial facilities only \$64 was obtained, what was not even enough to buy cardboard for new folders. In 2019 LWS did not get any financial support and it was decided to start a fundraising campaign to save the collection. Among different kinds of fundraising we choose reward-based crowdfunding with targeting on social media (i.e., facebook) and local media (i.e., local TV, online news channels, etc.).

Reward-based crowdfunding model has been applied because we understood that some part of backers will be out of interest in biological collections, however they can be involved by promising reward, price of which excide their minimal donation. Meaningful incentives are the key elements of a successful crowdfunding (Colombo et al. 2015), and we hoped that reward in form of limited series of wow-boxes will provide as with extra donations. We also chose facebook as main platform for our project and eliminated instagram, because we believed that facebook is better adjusted for such activities and their audience is represented by adults with better motivation. Moissejev (2013) pointed that backers support projects not only by providing funds but also by using social seals of approval (i.e., likes, shares, etc.). From other side, we believe that backers also make a decision based on such seals and presence of long-existing and well-filled accounts are crucial for successful fundraising. Neither AN nor MSN, we had no good insta accounts, therefore we also could not rely on them for crowdfunding.

The funding target was \$ 1.527 and minimal donation – \$ 2. While total price of 10 wow-boxes was about \$ 400, including extra content provided by later supporters (Sergii Glotov, Victoriia Janis, and Marharyta Zhujkova). We expected to obtain money for new herbarium folders, insecticides, fridge (allows to kill pests without destruction of DNA of herbarium samples), and windows for LWS. As a result of one-month campaign we received \$ 1.333, what correspond to rate of 87.3 % of success. However, the real success of campaign was much higher, because, as we mentioned, some people not only donated money but also proposed to donate their own works (e.g., books) to amplify the reward. From other side, some other people helped with sharing the information on media, provided us with better prices on cardboard (Ann Chanchikova), free herringbone tapes (Tetiana Khmil from LW herbarium) etc.

Our project showed that facebook is a good platform for crowdfunding, given us constantly donations for first 11 days and providing short tail of small donations for 8 days more. While other media resulted only short-term (1–2 days) fluctuations of donations, and were handled rather for updating of facebook campaign. We had two major backers (Nikolai Yunakov and Nikolay Iunakov), five middle backers (Olesia Bezsmertna, Mariia Tereschenko, Pavlo Zhukovski, Tamara Neimet, and Polina Bozhko) and 128 regular backers. Most of people (45.9 %) preferred to donate the amount that slightly exceed the minimal donation (\$ 4–8), and 21.5 % donated the amount that corresponded to this minimal adjusted pledge of \$ 2. Only 27.5 % of backers provided donations that surpassed this minimal amount more than in four times and, additionally, only 5.2 % of backers – surpassed it more than in 20 times. So, we can conclude that most of engaged audience was targeted on this adjusted minimal amount and only about third part of them was ready to offer much higher investment. This revealed that most of backers in our case were engaged rather in cluster of altruism than hedonism (Gierczak et al. 2016).

Despite of general success of crowdfunding campaign, LWS still seeks funds for two other windows and door that are almost out of order. Our project allowed to conserve the LWS collection at least for next five years, however did not solve general problem of absence of financial support. Moreover, directorate of museum decided not to provide such fundraising anymore due to reputation loses their experienced, so we have to find new ways to save the collection in future.

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Digitization of natural collections – the way to immortality

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Annotation: Оцифрування – це невідворотне майбутнє усіх природничих колекцій. На сьогодні не викликає сумніву і запитань необхідність оцифрування, особливо якщо це стосується рідкісних чи унікальних зразків, або ж малих колекцій, які наражені на найбільшу небезпеку зникнення. Якщо питання як і що саме оцифрувати залежить від спеціалістів окремих груп, то питання де і які дані згодом зберігати викликає чимало дискусій.

Keywords: *biodata, virtual collections, digitization, data providers, data aggregators.*

Ключові слова: *біодані, віртуальні колекції, оцифрування, провайдери, агрегат ори.*

It is even hard to estimate general circumscription of natural history collections. Comprehensive database GRSciColl lists 1,095 collections from 7,522 registered institutions across the world (Schindel et al. 2016). From 1.2 to 3 billions of specimens are suggested to be preserved in those collections (Ariño 2010, Vollmar et al. 2010). If follow another database, Index Herbariorum, 3,095 herbaria are registered for today in the world, and contain about 390 million specimens (Thiers 2019). However even this quite narrow fetch limited by plants is far away from real state of things. In 2019 Index Herbariorum listed for Ukraine only 23 herbaria with about 4 millions of specimens, while more precise investigation from 2011 already declared 59 herbarium collections with more than 4,3 millions of specimens (Shiyan 2011).

This testifies to the fact that there are still a lot of natural history collections hidden from us due to different reasons. Despite the fact that most important collections are well known and mainly included in databases at different level, small collections still contains important, sometimes even unique, vouchers. Absence of data from those collections in free access makes them higher endangered, because they remain to persist out of focus of scientific and public community and finally can be lost. Digitization of natural collections provides number of benefits including increased visibility and, as a result, higher enrolment of specimens in scientific research (Holovachov et al. 2014, Cantrill 2018). Of course, entries of virtual collections cannot replace original specimens, but they definitely amplify them and provide new opportunity for distribution of data (Drew 2011). In case of small collections that have a lack of financial support, imperfect

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01

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02

As a result of one-month campaign we received \$1,333, what corresponds to 87.3% of success.

However, the real success of campaign was much higher, because some people not only donated money but amplified the reward by own contribution.

We found that facebook is a good platform for crowdfunding, while other media showed only short-term (1–2 days) fluctuations of incomes.

Fig. 1. Incomes during campaign. Two peaks on 02.02 and 05.02 represent unusually high donations from three major backers. If not take them into account, we can see general regression with getting bottom already on 19th day (13.02).

Fig. 2. Fluctuation of incomes during the day. If not take into account 00:00 point (includes incomes with indeterminate time, e.g. given personally by cash) and artificial peaks generated at 17:00, 20:00 and 22:00 by three major backers, we can see that donations were evenly distributed during the day from 9:00 till 23:00 with slight decrease of activity from 11:00 till 14:00.

03

Most of people (45.9%) preferred to donate slightly more minimal amount (\$4–8), and 21.5% donated about estimated minimal pledge (\$2). Only 27.5% of donations surpassed minimal amount more than in 4 times. Hence, most of backers were classified in cluster of altruism (Gierczak et al. 2016).

04

Despite of general success of campaign, LWS still seeks funds for renovation. Our project allowed to conserve the LWS collection at least for next 5 years, but did not solve general problem of lack of financing.

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UP TO THE BIOSPHERE»**

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